

CULTURE-DEPENDENT EVALUATION OF THE RESPIRATORY MICROBIOME IN CHILDREN WITH CYSTIC FIBROSIS

Oksana Ishchenko✉

Department of Microbiology, Virology, Immunology and Epidemiology¹
med.oksana2017@gmail.com

Iryna Koshova

Department of Microbiology, Virology, Immunology and Epidemiology¹

Tetiana Krushinska

Department of Microbiology, Virology, Immunology and Epidemiology¹

Iryna Kolesnikova

Department of Epidemiology
Bogomolets National Medical University
13 Tarasa Shevchenko blvd, Kyiv, Ukraine, 01601

Dmytro Stepanyi

Department of Microbiology, Virology, Immunology and Epidemiology¹

¹Dnipro State Medical University

9 Volodymyra Vernadskoho str., Dnipro, Ukraine, 49044

✉ Corresponding author

Abstract

The study aimed to assess the regional peculiarities of the respiratory profile of children with cystic fibrosis (CF) in the Dnipro region (Ukraine).

Methods. Children living in the Dnipro region and aged younger than 18 years old with molecular-genetic confirmation of CF were enrolled in the study. Lung colonization was evaluated using a culture-dependent method. Sputum, mucus from the posterior pharyngeal wall and bronchoalveolar lavage fluid (BALF) were utilized.

Results. The *Firmicutes* phylum was the most common and occupied 54.00 % of the general proportion. On the other hand, the *Proteobacteria* phylum demonstrated overexpression in CF airways and kept the second rank with 28.87 %.

Sorensen's species similarity coefficient showed an allied affinity between the microbial burden of oropharyngeal samples with nasopharyngeal and sputum, QS = 0.61 and 0.91, respectively. However, the species composition within the nasal cavity was distinct from sputum and BALF (QS = 0.47).

The primary pathogens in childhood were *S. aureus*, *H. influenza*, *P. aeruginosa* and *A. fumigatus*. In contrast to gram-negative non-fermenters (GNNF), the prevalence of *S. aureus* isolates by age had a non-linear character. The commensal microbiota changed negatively with age. Among children under 12 years, the *Streptococcus* genus was identified in 23.08 % of the samples, but among the age category older than 15 – only in 9.22 %.

11.06 % of *S. aureus* had small colony variants (SCVs) morphotypes. Isolates of *P. aeruginosa* with the properties of SCVs were also found in children who underwent prolonged antimicrobial treatment. However, the most prominent was the mucoid phenotype – 34.31 % of isolates.

Conclusions. Along with conventional microbiological properties, obligate pathobionts in children with CF exhibited changes, resulting in difficulties in identification. These included auxotrophic modification into SCVs and mucoid transformation.

The culture-dependent technique gives crucial data about the profile of pathogens usually associated with CF, although it is sufficiently limited.

Keywords: cystic fibrosis, microbiome, minor colony variants, mucoid phenotype, resistance.

DOI: 10.21303/2504-5679.2022.002568

1. Introduction

Cystic fibrosis (CF) is an autosomal-recessive pathology resulting in pathognomonic changes in the respiratory microbiome and progressive deterioration of lung function [1]. The CF lung

environment is characterized by mucus obstruction and intense neutrophilic inflammation driving to anaerobic conditions that support the growth of facultative anaerobic and strictly anaerobic bacteria. In addition, repeated and prolonged courses of antimicrobial drugs provide selective pressure on the bacteria. *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* are multifaced microorganisms exhibiting various adaptive mechanisms and phenotypes, including changes in metabolism, resistance to antimicrobial drugs, and enhanced capacity for biofilm formation and anaerobic growth. Another adaptation lies in slight colony variants (SCV), which have been shown to typically occur during chronic infection and with extensive use of trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole [2, 3].

Simultaneously, the dysfunction of the cystic fibrosis conductance regulator (CFTR) also causes a progressive reduction of the commensal diversity in the respiratory tract [3–5]. Therefore, the CF lung microbiome may be a biomarker for follow-up and early intervention. In addition, the risk of early colonization by *P. aeruginosa* may be assessed on predictions within the microbiome. Three genera (*Streptococcus*, *Haemophilus*, and *Staphylococcus*) have emerged as predictive markers of antibiotic response [3, 5].

Molecular laboratory methods have opened new data about the microbial composition of airways in people with CF; however, the culture-based technique remains the method of choice under advanced and resource-limited conditions [1, 2]. These are reasonable if they aim to find obligate pathobionts associated with CF and assess their susceptibility to antimicrobials [1, 2, 6]. However, the lung microbiome is an attractive target for diagnostic tools, helping monitor the disease stage and being used to predict exacerbations [5].

The study aimed to assess the regional peculiarities of the respiratory profile of children with CF in the Dnipro region (Ukraine). Our focus was on microbial landscape, phenotypic modifications, and antimicrobial drug susceptibility.

2. Materials And Methods

The study was conducted at the department of microbiology, virology, immunology, and epidemiology (Dnipro State Medical University, Ukraine) from January 2019 to December 2021. Primary, the study was approved by the Bioethics Committee of the Dnipro State Medical University (protocol No. 8, 17.10.2018). Children living in the Dnipro region and aged younger than 18 years old with molecular-genetic confirmation of CF were enrolled in the study. Parents or healthcare proxies signed the Patient Informed Consent Form. According to the current recommendations, respiratory samples for the cultural assay were taken every three months and out of turn in case of an exacerbation. As the principal clinical specimens, sputum (spontaneous and inducible), mucus from the posterior pharyngeal wall and bronchoalveolar lavage fluid (BALF) were taken. Additionally, we sampled nasopharyngeal aspirate [6, 7].

The respiratory samples were taken before morning hygiene practices and preferably at least 12 hours after the last dose of antibiotics. Sputum and BALF were collected in sterile containers; swabs were collected in sterile tubes. The obtained biological material *extempore* was plated on a standard set of culture mediums. These included Colombian agar with 5 % sheep blood, mannitol-salt agar, MacConkey agar, chocolate agar, *Burkholderia cepacia* selective agar, selective agar for *Streptococcus*, cetrimide agar with glycerol and Sabouraud dextrose agar with chloramphenicol. For the cultivation of capnophiles and anaerobes, plates containing Schaedler agar with 5 % sheep blood were incubated in a GENbox jar under relevant atmospheric conditions. The plated Petri dishes were set on a thermostat for 24–72 hours at 37 °C; plates for fungi and anaerobes were incubating up to 1 week. The total microbial count was evaluated in CFU/ml, if possible. The yielded cultures were stained by Gram [6–8].

Identification of obtained isolates was performed considering morphological, tinctorial, cultural and biochemical properties according to Bergey's Manual of Systematic Bacteriology (2004). In addition, biochemical identification was made using relevant commercial kits (ErbaLachema, Chesh Republic).

Microsoft Office Excel 2010® with customizations was used for statistical data processing. Normality data distribution was evaluated by the Shapiro-Wilk test. For quantitative data with non-normal distribution, the Median and its interquartile range – Me (25 %; 75 %) were used. The Kruskal-Wallis test completed by the Mann-Whitney U-test was used to multiply quantitative data comparisons.

The results of the experiments were statistically significant at $p < 0.05$ [9]. Finally, Sorensen's species similarity coefficient was used to assess the covalence of the microbiome within different niches [10].

3. Results

3.1. Initial data

The study involved 32 children (16 boys and 16 girls) aged from 2 months to 17 years 10 months, the average age at the beginning of the study was 9.26 (0.35) years ($p = 0.697$). Among all, 28 children finished the study. Three participants left due to residence change, and one child was excluded because she had overgrown 18. Within 2019–2021, 315 respiratory samples were collected. The samples included sputum ($n = 121$), mucus from a smear from the posterior pharyngeal wall ($n = 182$), BALF ($n = 12$) and nasopharyngeal aspirates (relevant to oropharyngeal smears, $n = 182$). The distribution of the samples according to age was disproportionate, and the majority was obtained from children 6 – 12 years old because of the biggest sample size. There were no sputum samples from children under two years old because of imperfect cough reflexes; also, there was no need to collect BALF in the group.

There were 776 isolates obtained from children with CF in our study. All collected specimens were positive for microbiota; the monoculture was found in less than 2 % of cases ($n = 8$). The data is presented in **Table 1**. The overall prevalence of the obtained isolates comprised 2.5 for one determination. It was the biggest in children under two years old. However, it seems that the prevalence has increased by 15 years again. Nevertheless, there was a significant difference in its providers in early childhood compared to adolescence (look beyond).

Table 1

The distribution of the respiratory samples and recovered isolates according to age

Age category, years old	Samples		Isolates		Prevalence, 1 sample
	Absolute number, n	Proportion, %	Absolute number, n	Proportion, %	
Under 2	3	9.37	18	5.71	36
2–6	4	12.50	42	13.33	100
6–12	13	40.63	148	46.99	306
12–15	8	25.00	59	18.73	181
Over 15	4	12.50	48	15.24	153
Total	32	100.00	315	100.00	776

3.2. The general composition

In their most, the obtained isolates belonged to three phyla. The *Firmicutes* phylum was the most common and occupied 54.00 % of the general proportion. It was represented by *Staphylococcus spp.*, *Streptococcus spp.*, *Lactobacillus spp.*, *Aerococcus spp.* and obligate anaerobes *Peptostreptococcus spp.* and *Veilonella spp.*

Staphylococcus spp. ($n = 270$) was obtained from all patients involved in the study. The species composition of *Staphylococcus spp.* isolated from the respiratory tract included *S. aureus*, *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, *Staphylococcus haemolyticus*, *Staphylococcus intermedius*, *Staphylococcus lugdunensis* and *Staphylococcus saprophyticus*. Coagulase-positive isolates, particularly *S. aureus*, accounted for 83.70 %. All coagulase-negative species had approximately the same proportion and accounted for only 2–3 %. All children were periodically positive for

S. aureus and the culture were recovered from 71.75 % of the samples.

Streptococcus pyogenes, *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, and representatives of the *viridans* group, including *Streptococcus mitis*, *Streptococcus oralis*, *Streptococcus sanguinis*, and *Streptococcus anginosus*, were identified within *Streptococcus* genus. Cultures of *Streptococcus spp.* were identified in 22.86 % of the collected samples. Among catalase-negative cocci and the genus *Streptococcus*, 26 isolates were identified as *Aerococcus viridans*. The last was isolated from 8.25 % of the samples from the respiratory tracts of children with CF.

Peptostreptococcus spp. and *Veilonella spp.* occupied 6.06 % of the isolates and were cultured from only 14 % of the samples. In our study, obligate anaerobes were isolated in a smaller

amount than is usually described [3, 11, 12]. Even though we used anaerobic conditions and an enriched medium, it might be due to cultivation features that unintentionally were not considered. Concurrently, anaerobes in the CF airways are fewer than in non-CF lungs; consequently, the mentioned changes could be a characteristic of lung physiopathology under the dysfunction of CFTR [1, 13].

The *Proteobacteria* phylum demonstrated overexpression in CF-airways and kept the second rank with 28.87 %; *Neisseria spp.*, *Achromobacter spp.*, *Pseudomonas spp.*, *Klebsiella spp.*, *Escherichia spp.*, *Serratia spp.*, *Moraxella spp.*, *Haemophilus spp.* and *B. cepacia complex*. Gram-negative non-fermenters (GNNF) have a known adverse effect on CF patients' duration and quality of life [13, 14]. Among all isolates, their proportion was 17 %; cultures were isolated from one-third of the selected samples – 35.87 %. The species composition of the *Pseudomonas* genus was represented by *P. aeruginosa*, *Pseudomonas fluorescense*, and *Pseudomonas putida*. Note that the isolation of *P. fluorescense* and *P. putida* was episodic in some children, in quantities that were not etiologically significant. *P. aeruginosa* was isolated from 32.70 % of clinical specimens. Undoubtedly, such results indicate the presence in childhood of severe violation of eubiosis in the respiratory tract in CF.

The representatives of the *Enterobacteriales*, namely *Klebsiella spp.*, *Escherichia spp.* and *Serratia spp.* accounted for 2.71 % of isolates and were present in 6.67 % of samples. Significant age features characterized this taxon.

The *Actinobacteria* phylum was represented by *Corynebacterium spp.*; it counted only 2.44 % of isolates. The cultures were recovered from 4.44 % of clinical specimens. It is known that non-toxicogenic *Corynebacterium spp.* are among the main commensals of the upper respiratory tract; however, in our study, their proportion was significantly reduced compared to the general population.

The *Bacteroidetes* phyla counted 2.45 % and were represented by *Prevotella spp.* On the other hand, phyla *Fusobacteria* holds only 1.78 %.

Identified fungi were *Candida spp.* and *Aspergillus spp.*; they occupied 11.21 % of the general proportion. Yeasts were isolated from 22.22 % of samples; moulds – from 27.2 % of samples. The following species represented the *Candida* genus in descending order: *Candida albicans* (87 %), *Candida dubliniensis* and *Candida tropicalis*. Moreover, although the role of these microorganisms in the pathogenesis of CF remains debated, it was reported that *C. dubliniensis* might be associated with the progression of lung pathology [13]. Among all, 5.40 % of samples obtained from 4 participants were positive for *Aspergillus spp.* The species composition of the genus is *Aspergillus fumigatus* (71 %) and *Aspergillus flavus*.

Therefore, the respiratory tract microbiome in children with CF has been damaged. The respiratory tract contains a lack of commensals that potentially could provide colonization resistance against CF-associated pathogens. At the same time, the functioning of the deficient CFTR creates prerequisites for colonization by microorganisms that are not typical for the general population, such as *P. aeruginosa*, *B. cepacia complex*, *S. maltophilia*, and *Aspergillus spp.* These results are summarized and shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. The microbial landscape of airways in children with cystic fibrosis

3.3. Niche-dependent patterns of microbial composition

In the next stage of the study, our interest was driven by the comprehension that microorganisms living within different niches must cope with various stressors to survive and persist. The variations in humidity, the concentration of salts and immune factors result in differences in the microbial landscape of the upper and lower parts of the respiratory tract [13, 14].

S. aureus, *H. influenzae* and *P. aeruginosa* remained the leading pathogens collected from different loci of the respiratory tract. However, significant differences in upper and lower respiratory tract species were found.

In our study, the microbiome of the nasal cavity was depleted and represented by only a few taxones. From the nasal aspirates, *Staphylococcus spp.* was mainly recovered; it occupied 73.86 % of all isolates from the nasopharyngeal smears. Such traditional for the general population, catalase-negative cocci as *S. pneumoniae* and *A. viridans*, were isolated sporadically in our study; their proportion was 1.96 %. Similarly, the genus *Corynebacterium* also gave meagre growth; the culture was obtained from only 5.50 % of the collected samples, and the proportion of the isolates was 6.54 %. Among all cultures from this well-aerated niche, there were no obligate anaerobes or representatives of *Enterobacterales*. Sorensen's species similarity coefficient showed an allied affinity between the microbial burden of nasopharyngeal and oropharyngeal samples (QS = 0.61). However, the species composition within the nasal cavity was distinct from sputum and BALF (QS = 0.47).

Oropharyngeal smears were rich in concomitant microbiota, particularly commensals of the oral cavity such as *S. oralis*, *S. mitis* and *S. sanguinis*. Representatives of the *Corynebacterium* genus were also mostly isolated from oropharyngeal smears but in a significantly limited amount. At the same time, unlike samples from the nasopharynx, *Pseudomonas spp.*, *Haemophilus spp.*, *Moraxella spp.*, *B. cepacia complex*, and as *Enterobacteriaceae* and *Serratia spp.* families were obtained from oropharyngeal samples. Most of the obligate anaerobes were isolated from oropharyngeal samples; the genus *Prevotella spp.* was not secreted from BALF and sputum. There were no differences in the species composition of sputum and oropharyngeal swabs – QS = 0.91. A comparison of microbial diversity at different sites of the respiratory tract is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Microbial load of different types of smears collected from children with cystic fibrosis

3.4. Age-dependent patterns

The total microbial load did not differ significantly across all age groups and comprised 10^5 – 10^{12} CFU/ml. In our study, the primary pathogens in childhood were *S. aureus*, *H. influenzae*,

P. aeruginosa and *A. fumigatus*. The microbial diversity was higher in children under two and after 15 years, whereas there was a significant difference in the providers.

Predominantly, samples from participants under two years old belonged to *Firmicutes* and were found to be *Staphylococcus spp.*, *Streptococcus spp.*, *Peptostreptococcus spp.* and *Lactobacillus spp.* Despite the comparable diversity of commensal microbiota in this age, their respiratory microbiome has already been compromised due to the presence of *S. aureus* and representatives of the *Enterobacteriaceae* family. The youngest child in the study, aged four months, had a positive result for *S. aureus* in repeated controls. The culture of the pathogen was obtained from respiratory samples in an etiologically significant amount of 10^5 – 10^7 CFU/ml. These results indicate the early colonization of the respiratory tract by aggressive pathogens in CF. 26 children (81.25 %) had a positive bacteriological test for *S. aureus* at least three times a year, confirming chronic infection.

The prevalence of *S. aureus* isolates by age had a non-linear character (Fig. 3). Cultures were obtained from 27.78 % of samples from children under two years of age. However, there was a decreasing tendency among elder participants – 76.19–70.83 %. These changes may be caused by the progressive pathophysiological changes in the respiratory tract due to the dysfunction of CFTR and the selection of favourable conditions for further colonization by other prognostic pathogens with more developed adaptive and competitive properties [15, 16]. It has been estimated those other pathogens, particularly GNNF, had a linear prevalence in childhood. In our study, *M. catarrhalis*, *P. aeruginosa*, *A. xylooxidans*, and *B. cepacia complex* began their effects in early preschool age, but they were most common in the older age groups: 12–15 years – 54.24 %, older than 15 years – 77.08 %. The microorganism *P. aeruginosa* had the highest proportion, $R^2 = 0.9003$.

Fig. 3 The prevalence of respiratory pathogens in CF children of different age groups (% , $n = 315$)

We used *Leeds* criteria to stratify our participants. Among all, at the end of 2021, four children had at least three consecutive positive cultures of *P. aeruginosa* during the year and therefore had a chronic bronchopulmonary infection. Also, *P. aeruginosa* was isolated from four children in 2020 but not in 2021, so they had «infection in the past». Another four children had intermittent *P. aeruginosa* infection. The age of primary *P. aeruginosa* infection was three years and nine months, which is undoubtedly a very unfavourable prognostic factor. *B. cepacia complex* infection was detected in children over ten years of age. *A. xylooxidans* was cultured sporadically among children of older age groups.

The culture of *H. influenzae* was identified in samples from children aged two years and older. The microorganism was isolated from 16.67–23.73 % of the specimens. Usually, the pathogen was detected in association with *S. aureus* (49/62 (79.03 %)) and other purulent cocci.

In contrast to GNNF, the qualitative and quantitative characteristics of the commensal microbiota changed negatively with age. Among children under 12 years, the *Streptococcus* genus was

identified in 23.08 % of the samples, but among the age category older than 15 – only in 9.22 %. The proportion of the isolates in these age groups was 7.73 % and 4.53 %, respectively.

Corynebacterium spp. are representatives of commensal microbiota with a proven ability to confront gram-negative pathogens [1, 13]. In our study, the cultures were obtained similarly from all age groups, 4.71 (1.57) %.

The role of fungi in pulmonary pathology under the dysfunction of CFTR remains questionable. However, some data shows that moulds in airways are also linked with poor clinical outcomes [17–19]. There was *Aspergillus spp.* in our study. These fungi were found in an intermittent or consequent manner, so they were found reasonable to be considered and reported. Moulds were isolated from samples from children above six years, and the total prevalence of the pathogen was 5.4 %. Among all, 12.5 % of children ($n = 4$) were positive for moulds. Cultures were obtained from older children (mean age 12.5 (9.5; 15.7) years) with chronic *P. aeruginosa* infection.

3.5. Cultural peculiarities of microbes associated with CF

Usually, all isolates of *S. aureus* had typical cultural and biochemical properties (Fig. 4). However, we found isolates of SCVs *S. aureus* in 11.06 % of cases. 84 % of the cultures were yielded from children treated with aminoglycosides and/ or trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole. SCVs of *S. aureus* were always found in association with mucoid *P. aeruginosa*. *S. aureus* with the phenotype of SCVs appeared on a blood-containing culture medium after 48–72 hours of cultivation and produced tiny colonies without pigmentation and hemolytic zone; sometimes, they appear as «fried eggs». The reversion of *S. aureus* SCVs to the wild phenotype occurred after reseeded and cultivation under anaerobic conditions and/or at room temperature (time-dependent stability).

Fig. 4. Staphylococcus aureus with wild phenotype, 48 h on mannitol-salt agar

In our study, some microbial interaction was also observed. The absence of *S. aureus* in the presence of coagulase-negative representatives of the genus was noticed. Probably coagulase-negative *Staphylococcus spp.* has a suppressive effect on this pathobiont. However, on the other hand, the local immune profile should also be considered, particularly the salt-dependent activity of antimicrobial peptides. Nevertheless, in our study, *S. epidermidis*, *S. saprophyticus* and *S. haemolyticus* protected against *S. aureus* colonization or significantly limited the growth of the microorganism ($r_s = -0.725$; $p \leq 0.05$).

All *Pseudomonas* isolates had typical biochemical properties with inertness to most sugars; cultures of *P. aeruginosa* ($n = 103$) showed characteristic acylamidase activity. Isolates of *P. aeruginosa* with the properties of SCVs were found in children who underwent prolonged antimicrobial treatment. They appeared MacConkey or Endo agar after 72 hours of incubation as lactose-positive dry, waxy drops (Fig. 5). There was no visible hemolytic activity on blood agar. Also, pigmentation was absent. However, the most prominent was exactly the mucoid phenotype – 34.31 % of isolates (Fig. 6). Except for mucus production, also it was characterized by the absence or weak oxidase activity.

Fig. 5. Small colony variants of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, 72 h on Endo agar

Fig. 6. Mucoid colonies of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, 24 h on cetrimide agar with glycerol

P. aeruginosa was also associated with fungi. Both impaired physiology of airways and long-term and recurrent antibacterial therapy promotes the activation of fungi. Simultaneously, *P. aeruginosa* exerts an inhibitory effect on these microorganisms through siderophores and iron uptake from *Aspergillus spp.* However, fungi have mechanisms to avoid the inhibitory effect of the bacteria [18, 19]. In our study, the frequency rate of *Aspergillus spp.*, in combination with *P. aeruginosa* was 20.41 % and statistically significantly higher than in the group without the bacteria ($\chi^2 = 20.952$; $p < 0.001$). The associative link between infection *P. aeruginosa* and *Aspergillus spp.* was moderate, $\phi = 0.338$.

4. Discussion

Choosing an appropriate sample is essential for a reliable result. The nasal swabs were not helpful for the evaluation of the microbial composition of the lower respiratory tract. The significance of oropharyngeal swabs was equivalent to sputum and BALF; however, they were compromised by oral flora. Literature data supports that swabs from the posterior pharyngeal wall poorly reflect the microbial composition of the lungs [2, 19, 20]. BALF is the deepest and the most accurate sample but is invasive and requires general anaesthesia, especially in children. The collection of induced sputum is also limited because it requires the patient to be specially trained and may lead to bronchial spasms. So, spontaneous sputum is considered a sample of choice [6].

The next challenge for laboratory processing is highly viscous sputum due to defects in gene encoding CFTR with impairment of ion channels. In addition, CF sputum samples are often non-homogenous, with areas of purulence and mucus plugs that might catch microorganisms. Therefore, additional sputum treatment with solubilizing agents such as dithiothreitol is required [3, 21].

The CF lung microenvironment is polymicrobial and harbours fast-growing and slow-growing microorganisms having wild and auxotrophic phenotypes. Mucoid *P. aeruginosa* can overgrow slower-growing organisms or those present to a lesser extent. Selective culture mediums that inhibit the overgrowth of non-target bacteria and fungi can be helpful in the recovery of fastidious microorganisms. It can improve the detection of organisms present at a lower density. Several selective culture mediums are strongly recommended; these include selective culture medium for *B. cepacia complex*, mannitol salt or chromogenic agar for *S. aureus*, chocolate agar with cefsulodin for *H. influenza* and Sabouraud agar with chloramphenicol for fungi [3, 6, 13].

In the case of the presence of GNNF and other fast-growing bacteria, detection of other microbes is highly laborious. It requires additional human resources, financial outlay, equipment support and time but non-prognosis making. A routine medical practice requires information about obligate pathobionts associated with CF, and usually, commensals are not considered. Current data does not support a common use of additional culture conditions for CF clinical samples [6].

In our study, we routinely have been performing Gram staining every time, Ziehl-Nielsen one time a year and a case of prolonged macrolides course. The sensitivity of the acid-fast method significantly depends on bacterial load in the smear [6], and our study had no positive acid-fast staining results.

All GNNFs should be identified at the species level. Isolates of *P. aeruginosa* with typical characteristics can be reliably identified without additional tests. Using biochemical commercially available test kits supplemented by oxidase test and antibiogram can identify *S. maltophilia*, *Achromobacter spp.* and unpigmented *P. aeruginosa*. Commercial kits/systems should not be used to identify the *B. cepacia complex*. Identification of *B. cepacia complex*, atypical isolates of *S. maltophilia*, *Achromobacter spp.* and *P. aeruginosa*, and any colomycin-resistant non-fermentable gram-negative rods, must be confirmed by molecular-genetic methods [6, 7, 22, 23].

Limitations of the study. Limitations of the study include circumstances that unintentionally could be overlooked. BALF is a gold standard for the evaluation of the microbial composition of the lower respiratory tract. However, it is invasive, so it cannot be used routinely. The results of the bacteriological study also depend on the quality of the culture media and the presence of the relevant atmospheric conditions. However, routine procedures that complied with better practices could be compromised due to the fast-growing microorganisms able to overgrow the slow-growings. Also, non-cultivable microorganisms could be detected only with molecular-genetic methods. The same aspects could be transferred to identification methods.

Prospects for further research. Further prospective includes antimicrobial susceptibility testing of the pathobionts associated with CF. However, also microbial and host-microbiome interactions are in the scope of interest for future studies.

5. Conclusions

The respiratory microbiome in children with CF in the Dnipro region (Ukraine) is altered and harbours such dangerous pathogens as *P. aeruginosa*, *B. cepacia complex*, *S. aureus* and *Aspergillus spp.* Along with conventional microbiological properties, obligate pathobionts in children with CF exhibited changes, resulting in difficulties in identification. These included auxotrophic modification into SCVs after a prolonged course of antimicrobials and mucoid transformation in case of chronic infection or absence of oxidase in *P. aeruginosa*. Simultaneously, the normal lung microbiome was also significantly affected and had decreased diversity, with a progressive decline of commensals and rising obligate pathobionts associated with CF. Also, obligate anaerobes were found to a lesser extent than are usually described in a healthy state.

There were differences in the microbial composition of the upper and lower parts of the respiratory tract. The nasal cavity was the poorest, and *Staphylococcus spp.* was mostly recovered from such samples. There were only a few isolates of GNNF, so it makes these samples essential for microbiological surveillance in children with CF. There was a close affinity between a microbial spectrum of oral samples and sputum with tracheobronchial lavage waters. Therefore, obligate

pathobionts associated with CF were recovered from oropharyngeal samples, sputum, and lavage water in cognate qualitative indicators.

The culture-dependent technique is not absolute but gives crucial data about the microbial profile. It is associated with difficulties in identification and limits detection of non-culturing microbes and slow-growing bacteria or fungi.

However, it remains essential for the detection of the majority of pathogens usually associated with CF, their biofilm-producing properties, cultural and biochemical profile, as well as susceptibility to antimicrobial drugs.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest concerning this paper, as well as the published research results, including the financial aspects of conducting the research, obtaining, and using its results, as well as any non-financial personal relationships.

Financing

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

References

- [1] Lynch, S. V., Bruce, K. D. (2013). The Cystic Fibrosis Airway Microbiome. *Cold Spring Harbor Perspectives in Medicine*, 3 (3), a009738–a009738. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1101/cshperspect.a009738>
- [2] Gilpin, D., Hoffman, L. R., Ceppe, A., Muhlebach, M. S. (2021). Phenotypic characteristics of incident and chronic MRSA isolates in cystic fibrosis. *Journal of Cystic Fibrosis*, 20 (4), 692–698. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcf.2021.05.015>
- [3] Cuthbertson, L., Walker, A. W., Oliver, A. E., Rogers, G. B., Rivett, D. W., Hampton, T. H. et. al. (2020). Lung function and microbiota diversity in cystic fibrosis. *Microbiome*, 8 (1). doi: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40168-020-00810-3>
- [4] Françoise, A., Héry-Arnaud, G. (2020). The Microbiome in Cystic Fibrosis Pulmonary Disease. *Genes*, 11(5), 536. doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/genes11050536>
- [5] Scialo, F., Amato, F., Cernera, G., Gelzo, M., Zarrilli, F., Comegna, M. et. al. (2021). Lung Microbiome in Cystic Fibrosis. *Life*, 11 (2), 94. doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/life11020094>
- [6] Burns, J. L., Rolain, J.-M. (2014). Culture-based diagnostic microbiology in cystic fibrosis: Can we simplify the complexity? *Journal of Cystic Fibrosis*, 13 (1), 1–9. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcf.2013.09.004>
- [7] Royal Brompton Hospital Paediatric Cystic Fibrosis Team. Clinical guidelines: Care of children with cystic fibrosis (2022). Medicines Management Board of Royal Brompton & Harefield NHS Foundation Trust 2020, 311.
- [8] Cornaglia, G., Courcol, R., Hermann, J.-L. et. al. (2011). ESCMID: European Manual of Clinical Microbiology.
- [9] Yadav, S. K., Singh, S., Gupta, R. (2019). *Biomedical Statistics. A Beginner's Guide*. Singapore: Springer, 342. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-32-9294-9>
- [10] Sait, L., Galic, M., Strugnelli, R. A., Janssen, P. H. (2003). Secretory Antibodies Do Not Affect the Composition of the Bacterial Microbiota in the Terminal Ileum of 10-Week-Old Mice. *Applied and Environmental Microbiology*, 69 (4), 2100–2109. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1128/aem.69.4.2100-2109.2003>
- [11] Thornton, C. S., Surette, M. G. (2021). Potential Contributions of Anaerobes in Cystic Fibrosis Airways. *Journal of Clinical Microbiology*, 59 (3). doi: <https://doi.org/10.1128/jcm.01813-19>
- [12] Frayman, K. B., Armstrong, D. S., Grimwood, K., Ranganathan, S. C. (2017). The airway microbiota in early cystic fibrosis lung disease. *Pediatric Pulmonology*, 52 (11), 1384–1404. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1002/ppul.23782>
- [13] Hardy, B. L., Merrell, D. S. (2021). Friend or Foe: Interbacterial Competition in the Nasal Cavity. *Journal of Bacteriology*, 203 (5). doi: <https://doi.org/10.1128/jb.00480-20>
- [14] Krishnakumari, V., Guru, A., Adicherla, H., Nagaraj, R. (2018). Effects of increasing hydrophobicity by N-terminal myristoylation on the antibacterial and hemolytic activities of the C-terminal cationic segments of human- β -defensins 1–3. *Chemical Biology & Drug Design*, 92 (2), 1504–1513. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1111/cbdd.13317>
- [15] Bhagirath, A. Y., Li, Y., Somayajula, D., Dadashi, M., Badr, S., Duan, K. (2016). Cystic fibrosis lung environment and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* infection. *BMC Pulmonary Medicine*, 16 (1). doi: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12890-016-0339-5>
- [16] Clunes, M. T., Boucher, R. C. (2007). Cystic fibrosis: the mechanisms of pathogenesis of an inherited lung disorder. *Drug Discovery Today: Disease Mechanisms*, 4 (2), 63–72. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ddmec.2007.09.001>
- [17] Martín-Gómez, M. T. (2020). Taking a look on fungi in cystic fibrosis: More questions than answers. *Revista Iberoamericana de Micología*, 37 (1), 17–23. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.riam.2019.10.004>

- [18] Singh, A., Ralhan, A., Schwarz, C., Hartl, D., Hector, A. (2017). Fungal Pathogens in CF Airways: Leave or Treat? *Mycopathologia*, 183 (1), 119–137. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11046-017-0184-y>
- [19] Poore, T. S., Hong, G., Zemanick, E. T. (2021). Fungal Infection and Inflammation in Cystic Fibrosis. *Pathogens*, 10 (5), 618. doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/pathogens10050618>
- [20] Goddard, A. F., Staudinger, B. J., Dowd, S. E., Joshi-Datar, A., Wolcott, R. D., Aitken, M. L. et. al. (2012). Direct sampling of cystic fibrosis lungs indicates that DNA-based analyses of upper-airway specimens can misrepresent lung microbiota. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 109 (34), 13769–13774. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1107435109>
- [21] Hector, A., Jonas, F., Kappler, M., Feilcke, M., Hartl, D., Griese, M. (2009). Novel Method to Process Cystic Fibrosis Sputum for Determination of Oxidative State. *Respiration*, 80 (5), 393–400. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1159/000271607>
- [22] Sibley, C. D., Grinwis, M. E., Field, T. R., Eshaghurshan, C. S., Faria, M. M., Dowd, S. E. et. al. (2011). Culture Enriched Molecular Profiling of the Cystic Fibrosis Airway Microbiome. *PLoS ONE*, 6 (7), e22702. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0022702>
- [23] Caballero, J. de D., del Campo, R., Tato, M., Gómez G de la Pedrosa, E., Cobo, M., López-Causapé, C. et. al. (2014). Microbiological diagnostic procedures for respiratory cystic fibrosis samples in Spain: towards standard of care practices. *BMC Microbiology*, 14 (1). doi: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12866-014-0335-y>

Received date 09.06.2022

Accepted date 21.07.2022

Published date 31.07.2022

© The Author(s) 2022

This is an open access article
under the Creative Commons CC BY license

How to cite: *Ishchenko, O., Koshova, I., Krushinska, T., Kolesnikova, I., Stepanyi, D. (2022). Culture-dependent evaluation of the respiratory microbiome in children with cystic fibrosis. EUREKA: Health Sciences, 4, 39–49. doi: <http://doi.org/10.21303/2504-5679.2022.002568>*